

Khmer Traditional New Year (Choul Chnam Khmer)

also known as “Moha Sangkran”, “Pun Chol Chnam”, “Chol Chnam Thmey”, “Sangkran Chnam Thmey”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Sri Lankan Buddhist Groups, Mainland Southeast Asian Buddhist Traditions, Language, Austroasiatic, Khmeric, Central Khmer

Khmer Traditional New Year is the Khmer-culturally specific name for the solar new year of Southern Asia (Sri Lanka through Mekong Vietnam). The holiday primarily serves as a marker of agricultural cycles, spanning three days, and typically beginning on April 13 or 14. “Entering the New Year” (Chol Chnam Thmey) marks the end of the harvest season, a period during which farmers often enjoy increased income. Workers from all parts of the country and outside, particularly in urban centers, return to their home villages for family reunions during the New Year. Celebrations feature rituals and activities such as receiving blessing from Buddhist monks, worshiping the goddess of the New Year, food donations to Buddhist monasteries, the Srang Preah water-pouring ceremony, eating traditional foods like kralan (sticky rice cake mixed with other ingredients, stuffed into bamboo sections, and roasted over a wood fire), partying with alcoholic drinks, playing traditional games, and dancing. While contemporary Khmer New Year celebrations are situated within Buddhism, other components—such as the legend of the New Year involving Kabil Moha Pram (Kabala Phom in Lao and Thai; Brahma King Arsi in Burmese)—originate from Brahmanism/Hinduism. Key elements of Khmer New Year celebrations, especially songs and dances like ramvong and salavan, also derive from Laos and Northeastern Thailand. Traditional games are also a highlight of during the three-day celebration as they bring communities together. Popular games include Chol Chhoung (groups tossing a scarf, with hit players singing and dancing to retrieve it), Bos Angkunnh (throwing seeds to hit targets, losers getting knees tapped), Leak Kanseng (circle game dropping a towel like Duck Duck Goose), Teanh Prot (a recognized UNESCO Intangible Heritage game; tug-of-war symbolizing the Churning of the Ocean of Milk), and Chap Kon Kleng (hen protecting chicks from hawk). Despite these cultural specificities, certain practices of Khmer New Year are shared across Southern Asia. The celebration coincides with solar New Year observances across South and Southeast Asia, including in India, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Laos, Cambodia, southern Vietnam, and China’s Yunnan Province, where Theravada Buddhist culture is interwoven with local traditions.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Cambodia

Region tags: Cambodia

This region represents Cambodia in its present-day territorial integrity, inclusive of the mainland and

several outlying islands (koh) in the Gulf of Thailand.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

↳ Enclosed?

– No

Notes: There are rituals that take place at people's houses. It is called Tatoul Devada Chhnam Thmey (greetings new year goddess), which families clean the house thoroughly and set up an altar with flowers, incense, and food, marking the home as a purified space ready to receive the New Year angel and ancestral spirits.

– Yes

Notes: Khmer New Year rituals are spatially structured around key places in the Khmer social and cosmological landscape: the house, its thresholds, the spirit shrine, the pagoda (Wat) compound, and, in some regions, water sources and monumental sites like ancient temples.

↳ Elevated?

– Yes

↳ By a body of water?

– No

– Yes

Notes: Another ritual called Srang Preah (water-pouring) is for bodily and spatial cleansing (house, Buddha images, elders' bodies). In some places, reservoirs are used for Srang Preah-type water-pouring and bathing rites, drawing on older associations of water with purification and renewal.

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: While pagodas are sacred, their courtyards also become vibrant centers for social interaction. After religious ceremonies, people of all ages engage in traditional folk games like Chol Chhoung (scarf tossing), Leak Kanseng (hiding the towel), and Angkunn (seed tossing), while cultural performances and Roam Vong circle dancing unfold in the beautifully decorated temple grounds

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Rituals within the pagoda compound include offering food to monks, Pithi Phnom Khsach (building sand stupas), Pithi Srang Preah (bathing Buddha statues), and Bang Skoa (ancestor veneration). Pagodas, believed to be spiritually cleansed and visually well decorated, become the main venue for merit-making, which include the acts of offering food to monks, listening to chanting, and erecting ritual sand stupas in the temple grounds.

↳ Other [Specify]

– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– Yes

↳ Underground?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building)

– No

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Notes: It usually take place inside Buddhist monasteries

– Yes

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual for receiving the New Year angel and ancestral spirits usually take place in a private place

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– Yes

↳ Through divination:

– No

↳ Through astronomical observation:

– No

↳ Through myths, legends or literature:

– Yes

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– No

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– Yes

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Field Doesn't Know

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

↳ Daily:

– No

↳ Weekly:

– No

↳ Seasonally:

– No

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

↳ Special events/occasions:

– No

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Notes: There are three days of celebration: -Day 1: Maha Sangkran (The Entrance) marks the arrival of a new "Angel" (Tevada) to take charge of the world for the year. Day 2: Virak Vanabat (Day of Offering), which concentrates on charity and honoring elders and ancestors. Day 3: Vearak Loeng Sak (The Official Start), which is the official transition into the new year, characterized by spiritual cleansing.

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 2

Notes: Key religious and spiritual rituals during Khmer New Year include Maha Sangkran (welcoming the new deity), Pithi Phnom Khsach (building sand stupas), Pithi Srang Preah (bathing rituals), and Baat Preah (offerings to monks). Each typically lasts up to two hours.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Notes: These agents include celestial deities, religious figures (monks and lay Buddhist master (achar), and family members, each performing specific roles.

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 20

Notes: Khmer New Year rituals vary according to the type of ritual being celebrated. Food-offering blessings inside the pagoda often involve over a hundred people, as every family in the village typically participates. Rituals like receiving the New Year goddess at people's homes usually involve between 5 and 20 people.

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– No

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– Specify: 50 or older

Notes: They include Buddhist monks, lay Buddhist master (achar), and family members

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– Yes

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– Yes

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: These include the Welcoming Rituals and Self-Purification which are typically carried out by family members who are not specialists.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Age: normally only elders perform the rituals

– Religious affiliation or status: Buddhists only

– Physical state (e.g. menstruation, illness): illness or disable

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They are involvements of the New Year Angel (Tevada Chnam Thmey), which is one of the seven daughters of the legendary god-king Kabil Moha Prum, descends annually to oversee the world, with the specific angel determined by the weekday the festival begins. New Year Angels by Weekday: Tungsa Tevy (Sunday): Adorned with rubies, rides a Garuda. Koreak Tevy (Monday): Adorned with pearls, rides a tiger. Reaksa Tevy (Tuesday): Carries a trident, rides a horse. Mondar Tevy (Wednesday): Rides a donkey. Keriny Tevy (Thursday): Rides an elephant. Khemara Tevy (Friday): Protectress of musicians, rides a buffalo. Mohurea Tevy (Saturday): Rides a peacock. Kabil Moha Prum, the King of the Gods, features in the myth where his daughters carry his severed head in a celestial procession to avert global catastrophe such as burning the earth or drying the oceans. The legend also involves Dhammabal Koma, a clever young man whose riddle-solving skills helped establish the festival's traditions.

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– No

Notes: They are mythical/imaginative figures

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they animals:

– Yes

Notes: In the Kabil Moha Prum story, there are involvements of births

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

Notes: Banana leaves, banana, apple, organ, longan, durian, jackfruit, and coconut are used in most of the new year rituals

↳ Other:

– Specify: Homes set up a special altar (often outside) decorated with candles, incense, and fresh flowers like lotus or jasmine

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

Notes: The New Year Angel (Tevada Chnam Thmey) is the highest goddess of the new year

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– Specify: 50-100

Notes: During Khmer New Year, a crowd of this nature is most likely gathered at a Buddhist Pagoda (Wat) or a public park designated for cultural festivities.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– No

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– Specify: 7-85

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: can't speak too loud and have to pay respects at all times

- ↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?
 - No

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

- No

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

- Yes

- ↳ Is it individually determined:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it communally determined:
 - Yes [specify]: Usually people come together within a village

Is participation obligatory?

- No

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

- Yes

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

- Yes

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

- Yes

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– Yes

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve ritual correction?

– No

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be positive:

– No

↳ Is the change expected to be negative:

– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral:

– Yes

↳ Select the type of change:

– Social

– Cultural

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– No

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ For deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ For ancestors:

– Yes

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– No

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Khmer New year rituals primarily appease multiple spiritual entities through offerings, cleansing, and merit-making, and they include ancestors and neak ta (local spirits), New Year Angel, the Buddha and monks, and elders.

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– No

↳ Is it mental:

– Yes

↳ Is it emotional:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– Yes

↳ During a specific illness?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

↳ Is it psychological:
– Yes

↳ Is it emotional:
– Yes

↳ Is it social:
– No

↳ Is it cultural:
– No

↳ Is it sexual:
– No

↳ Is it energetic:
– Yes

↳ is it environmental:
– No

↳ Is it spiritual:
– Yes

↳ During anxiety:
– Yes

↳ During depression:
– Yes

↳ During an injury?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

↳ Is it psychological:

– No

↳ Is it spiritual:

– Yes

↳ To improve fertility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve longevity?

– Yes

↳ To support development/growth?

– Yes

↳ To achieve vitality?

– Yes

↳ To improve virility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve resurrection?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– Yes

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– Yes

↳ To increase the amount of rain for agricultural/horticultural productivity:

– Yes

↳ For crop success:

– Yes

↳ For livestock success:

– Yes

↳ For success in gathering:

– Yes

↳ For success in fishing:

– No

↳ For success in hunting:

– No

↳ For industrial productivity:

– Yes

↳ For success in commerce/mercantilism/market exchange:

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– Yes

↳ To cause death:

– Yes

↳ To cause illness:

– Yes

↳ To cause bad luck:

– Yes

↳ To cause curses/hexes:

– Yes

↳ To destroy resources:

– No

↳ To destroy status:

– No

↳ To cause social harm:

– No

↳ To cause psychological harm:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

↳ As part of a celebration:

– Yes

↳ For love:

– Yes

↳ For social coordination:

– Yes

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– Yes

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– Yes

↳ For professional success (e.g., exam, promotion):

– Yes

↳ For legal success:

– No

↳ To obtain income/wealth:

– Yes

↳ To escape debt:

– Yes

- ↳ For business success:
 - Yes
- ↳ To recover lost objects:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other:
 - N/A

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

- ↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:
 - No

- ↳ Further ritual checks:
 - No

- ↳ Other:
 - N/A

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– No

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

–Specify: hundreds

Notes: A single community pagoda may host anywhere from hundreds to several thousand people at a time for communal alms-giving or sand stupa building. At home, rituals like welcoming the New Year Angel usually involve the entire immediate and extended family, often ranging from 5 to 15 people depending on household size. Group sizes for traditional folk games vary by activity, typically ranging from 50 to several hundred participants.

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– Yes

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– Yes

Notes: Depends of the type of dance

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– Yes

Notes: Again, this depends on the type of dance

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– Yes

↳ It involves kneeling:

– Yes

↳ It involves prostrating:

– No

↳ Does it involve remaining immobile:

– Yes

Notes: People don't move when they are receiving blessings from monks

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– Yes

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– Yes

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– Yes

↳ Is the procession one way?

– Yes

↳ Is the procession multidirectional?

– No

↳ Is the procession a roundtrip?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– Yes

↳ What is the distance covered (in kilometers)?

– Specify: 0.2

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it choreographed?

– No

↳ Is it a narrative?

– Yes

↳ Is it restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it involuntary? (caused by trance, etc.)

– Yes

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– No

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they totems:

– No

↳ Are they religious icons:

– Yes

Notes: Monks and the Buddha

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

↳ Are they vessels:

– No

↳ Are they masks:

– No

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– Yes

Notes: Usually Buddhist flags or Buddha images

- ↳ Other:
 - N/A

- ↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?
 - No

- ↳ Is text used during this ritual?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it a diagram:
 - No

 - ↳ Is it an inscribed item:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it a book:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it a scroll:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it a tablet:
 - No

 - ↳ Is it memorized text:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: In many occasions, they cook pork or chicken to bring to donate to Buddhist monks. As the primary spiritual agents, monks consume these fresh dishes devotees bring to the pagoda. While the physical food remains, the spirits of the dead are believed to consume its spiritual essence during the Bang Skoa ceremony. After offerings to monks or the New Year Angel at the home altar, the remaining food is shared among achar (lay Buddhist masters), elders, family, and friends during large communal feasts in the pagoda, regarded as consuming “blessed” food.

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is water used?

– Yes

↳ Is earth used?

– No

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

↳ Is fire used?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoke:

– No

↳ Is it incense:

– Yes

↳ Is it candle(s):

– Yes

↳ Is it torch(es):

– No

↳ Is it burnt objects like paper, leaves, or wood:

– No

↳ Is it a large fire:

– No

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– No

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– No

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– No

- ↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?
 - No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

- ↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?
 - Specify: 50

- ↳ Is food consumed?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it human:
 - Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it a non-human animal:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it a plant:
 - No

- ↳ Is it a fungus:
 - No

- ↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?
 - No

- ↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?
 - No

- ↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?
 - No

- ↳ In what state is the food consumed?
 - Cooked

- ↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it sacralized food?
 - No

- ↳ Is it symbolic food?
 - e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept
 - No

- ↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?
 - No

- ↳ Does food consumption happen on site?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?
 - Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?
– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?
– Yes

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?
– Yes

↳ Reducing wastefulness:
– Yes

↳ Mindful eating:
– Yes

↳ Vegetarianism:
– No

↳ Other:
– N/A

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?
– No

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?
– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?
– No

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– Yes

↳ Does the individual retain biographical identity?

– Yes

↳ Does the individual retain control of the body?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve spirit travel?

– No

↳ Is the individual chosen (e.g., by a supernatural agent)?

– No

↳ Is there a method of induction?

– No

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– No

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

Notes: People donate money to Buddhist monks and lay Buddhist masters

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

Notes: People consume food offerings at the end of the rituals

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– Yes

↳ Is there a substitution used to represent the symbolic offerings?

– No

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are animals offered?

– No

Notes: Khmer New Year rituals do not involve animal slaughter or killing. No ritualistic animal sacrifices occur in villages during the festival.

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: People usual offer soft drinks and drinking water. Rituals outside the pagoda compound and do not involve Buddhist monks typically involve alcoholic drinks.

- ↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?
 - No
- ↳ Are commodities offered?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Tea, coffee, and fruits are also offered
- ↳ Are household items offered?
 - No
- ↳ Are personal items offered?
 - No
- ↳ Is clothing offered?
 - No
- ↳ Are musical instrument offered?
 - No
- ↳ Are texts offered?
 - No
- ↳ Are weapons offered?
 - No
- ↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?
 - Yes

Notes: People offer money to Buddhist monks and lay Buddhist masters (achar) as part of the rituals. The allocation depends on each pagoda's arrangements: funds may go to individual monks and masters as private assets or to the temple for collective expenditures.

↳ Are precious substances offered?
– No

↳ Other:
– N/A

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?
– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?
– Yes

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?
– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?
– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?
– No

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?
– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– Low

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity

– Medium

Notes: People are instructed to avoid bad behavior, including arguing and insulting others

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– No

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of entrainment?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment emerging endogenously between participants in the ritual?
(e.g., clapping, chanting without external stimulus)

– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment to an external stimulus?

(e.g., a ritual leader, a musical beat)

– Yes

↳ Does the entrainment induce emotional conformity?

– Yes

Notes: This happens especially at Buddhist ceremonies, where participants conform to the roles and behaviors prescribed by ritual organizers—most often Buddhist monks and elders

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

–Specify: 60

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– No

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– Specify: Cambodian riel

Notes: American dollars are also used in some places

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– Specify: can be up to 50 people or more

